

Recommended citation: Laperrouza, M. (2018). Assessing transversal skills in the framework of an interdisciplinary program. In Clark, R., Munkebo Hussmann, P., Järvinen, H.-M., Murphy, M., & Etchells Vigild, M. (Eds.), *Creativity, Innovation and Entrepreneurship for Engineering Education Excellence. SEFI 46th Annual Conference* (pp. 968-975). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Brussels, Belgium. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14672748.

Assessing transversal skills in an interdisciplinary programme

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Conference Key Areas: Curriculum Development, Teaching Creativity & Innovation, Innovative Teaching and Learning Methods

Keywords: assessment, interdisciplinary, transversal skills, reflexivity

INTRODUCTION

The paper discusses the assessment of transversal skills in the framework of a 9-month interdisciplinary programme – the China Hardware Innovation Camp (CHIC) – that runs across 3 institutions in Switzerland and includes a short-term study abroad (STSA) in China. The programme has the particularity of having teams composed of engineering students (3), design students (2) and business students (1) affiliated with one of the 3 institutions and working together to develop an Internet of Things (IoT) device. The pedagogical scenario builds on a “learn-practice-reflect” framework. While limited to one-sixth of the project’s assessment, significant emphasis is placed on the development of transversal skills for engineering students. The assessment strategy makes heavy use of reflexive notes.

The paper presents the pedagogical scenario underlying the programme as well as the protocol to assess the transversal learning outcomes for the engineering students involved in the programme. It discusses a sub-set of the transversal skills assessment strategy, namely reflexivity. It suggests that reflexivity needs to be trained and maintained throughout the programme through different formats. It raises a number of questions related to the use of reflexivity as an assessment strategy for transversal skills in the context of an interdisciplinary programme.

1 PROGRAMME OVERVIEW

1.1 Brief description of the programme

The CHIC programme proposes to go “from idea to functional prototype in 30 working days”. Teams receive a blank sheet of A3 paper at the beginning of the programme and have 3 semesters to conceive, develop and prototype an IoT device.

1.2 Architecture of the programme

The programme is offered as an interdisciplinary Minor (30 ECTS) at the Master level at EPFL¹. It runs through the first three semesters of the Master. It takes place mainly in Switzerland but includes a 16-days prototyping sprint in a Chinese factory.

Credits for the programme are divided in two categories:

- Project-related (18 ECTS); each student works on a project within an interdisciplinary team; 3 out of the 18 ECTS are devoted to transversal skills;
- Technology-related (12 ECTS); students have to choose courses from a pre-established list; they can propose additional courses that are necessary to the completion of their project; courses can be taken during any of the three semesters.

In addition, students are to follow a 2-semester long humanities-related course (“Global perspectives, local realities”) aimed at contextualizing their techno-scientific project.

1.3 Underlying pedagogical aspects

The programme has been crafted with a number of pedagogical dimensions in mind:

- Bottom-up: projects are proposed by the students themselves; in essence, teams are given total liberty as to the problem their device aims to solve;
- Double-interdisciplinarity; engineering students originate from different sections and faculties (e.g., computer science, mechanical engineering and micro-engineering); in addition they work in a team with one business school from a neighbouring university and with one industrial designer and one media interaction designer from a neighbouring design school;
- Real world, real learning: while not aimed at being commercialized, projects must demonstrate a commercial potential and economic feasibility; teams simulate most of the aspects involved in developing a hardware device (e.g., business models, industrialisation, pitching to investors, etc.);
- Immersion; the initial development of the device’s prototype takes place in Switzerland; the teams are flown to Southern China (Shenzhen and Hong Kong) to improve their prototype and run a small-batch production at the end of the second semester; the STSA allows to extend the learning experience from cross-boundary to cross-cultural;
- Reflexivity; students are asked to reflect on different aspects of their learning throughout the programme both in terms of process and result.

In short, the programme is project-based, interdisciplinary, multi-site and student-driven. Immersion aside, it can be assimilated to new product development project-based programmes [1]. While being asked to step outside of their comfort zone, students seem to particularly appreciate owning a project from beginning to end, working in interdisciplinary teams and looking at a theme from different perspectives.

1.4 Mixed learning outcomes

The high-level learning outcomes of the programme have been divided into:

- Disciplinary: define functional requirements of a connected device, apply a structured approach to product development and realize a functional prototype;

¹ It is offered at the Master level in the neighbouring business school (HEC Lausanne) and at the Bachelor level at the design school (ECAL).

- Transversal: communicate effectively with professionals from other disciplines, write a scientific or technical report, identify the different roles that are involved in well-functioning teams and assume different roles, including leadership roles, apply fast prototyping techniques and technologies, pitch a product in front of different audiences, communicate effectively across different languages and cultures.

The nature of the programme implies that students are exposed to various management issues, including project management, teamwork, meeting management and cross-cultural management. Put differently, the development of the device becomes a vehicle to apply technical skills already or in the process of being mastered and to acquire new transversal skills.

1.5 Teaching strategies

Material related to transversal skills is taught exclusively through workshops. Their length varies from 3 hours (e.g., for pitching) to 2 days (e.g., for teamwork).

Teams are given significant autonomy to organize their work within a structured framework. For instance, the monthly milestones are built round a detailed set of deliverables; the latter are decomposed in weekly tasks. In addition to the provided “development roadmap”, teams can access resources related to the tasks – a resource can be related to a scientific/technical or to a transversal dimension. Faculty members initially created these resources. At the end of each edition, students work in pairs to either improve an existing resource or create a new resource they felt was missing in their project.

1.6 Motivation of the paper

In a sense the paper aims to answer a question raised by a colleague in a working group on open-ended projects. His question was the following: “how to make sure that students really learn transversal skills in multidisciplinary projects?” My initial answer to the question was “you can’t but I’ll will show you the assessment mechanism I put in place”. A number of deeper reasons are driving the paper:

- Transversal skills were defined as central learning outcomes in the programme and must therefore be assessed;
- The weight given to the transversal skills in the programme’s overall architecture remains limited (3 ECTS) but students tend to perceive them as one of the key benefit of the programme;
- Transversal skills and more specifically reflexivity about transversal skills are at times a scarce resource in the training of engineers;
- Interdisciplinarity is not a given; in other words, putting students from different disciplines around a table does not make an interdisciplinary team, nor does it ensure that students have benefitted from their exposure to different disciplines;
- In light of the resource-intensive nature of the programme, a valid question to ask is whether one can demonstrate “significant” learning in terms of transversal skills or if these could be achieved differently than through an interdisciplinary programme [2].

Questioning the acquisition of transversal skills in the framework of an interdisciplinary programme (and the associated assessment) is therefore at the core of the paper. As such it aims to build on the question of transferability enunciated in Ivanitskaya et al. with a focus on transversal skills in the context of an interdisciplinary programme [3].

2 ASSESSMENT OF TRANSVERSAL SKILLS

2.1 General protocol

Given the limited number of students participating in the programme each year (10-12 engineers and 10-12 non-engineers), emphasis is put on a qualitative assessment of the learning outcomes related to transversal skills. The transversal skills are evaluated through various means (see Table 1) including oral presentations at the time of milestones, individual reflexive notes at the end of the second and third semester and documentation of activities during the whole programme (e.g., blog posts of project progress).

Table 1. Overall assessment scheme

	MA1	MA2	MA3
Disciplinary skills (5/6)	Project preparation	Project realisation	Project finalisation
Transversal skills (1/6)	Oral presentation and reflexive note on group work	Oral presentations, reflexive note on group work and project management, documentation of activities	Oral presentations, reflexive note on group work, cross-cultural management, mentoring and documentation of activities

At each milestone (MS) students are to fill a spreadsheet, documenting what they learned so far regarding their own discipline, other disciplines, group work, project management and themselves. The spreadsheet is common to all team members and accompanies them throughout the programme.

Table 2. Selected comments from an engineer (MS 2 and 3, 2017-2018)

	My discipline	Other disciplines	Group work	Project management	Myself
MS2	Starting to discuss the electronics is exciting as it forces us to decide which will be the limits of our product	Having good visuals of the product doesn't only nicely illustrate our idea, it is also a way to get a more precise and relevant feedback	Discussions within the team were not necessarily easy with the distance / during the break	It might take some time for some ideas to mature in other persons' minds. Patience can be rewarding!	I was awed at the fact that working (meaning sleep deprivation before deadline) with the group sometimes felt very natural and fun
MS3	I realized how little flexibility Apple gave us to work. The 3D printing went very well and it is good to know that we have this option but it definitely won't resolve most of our prototyping issues	I learnt that the design and the creative process was sometimes a lot longer than I first thought	I feel that we start to really know how we work with each other and we did a good job separating the tasks and preparing for the presentation	I feel like we are a little bit stuck with some of the perspectives in the project but it will be easy to catch up the delay later on	Milestones are really a good way to make us realise the state of advancement of the project

A cross-cultural dimension is added for the milestone at the end of the China trip. This dimension is further explored as students work in pairs to document one theme on both sides of the Hong Kong-Shenzhen border (1'000 words). Themes include makerspaces, mass transit, the sharing economy, social media, innovation parks, migrant workers, etc. For this activity, engineering students can only pair with non-engineering students and work with someone outside of their project team. In addition a slightly adapted version of the Readiness for Interprofessional Learning Scale (RIPLS) questionnaire has been administered to all students at the very beginning of the programme during the past 2 editions (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Adapted RIPLS questionnaire (agree/strongly agree)

2.2 Reflexive notes

Reflexive notes are required at the end of the second and third semester. Both are meant to link the workshops and the work conducted on the project. The final assignment consists in writing a short essay (1'000 words) on:

- The student's personal reflections on their own team experience;
- The mentor-mentee relationship, and how the student could draw from their own experience in order to guide their mentee;
- How this mentoring relationship helped the student understand one's team dynamics or how it might be beneficial in the future.

Given the structure of the programme, students from 2 consecutive editions "overlap" during one semester. This provides the opportunity to put to use the skills acquired by the first batch of the students to "accompany" the second batch. This has been operationalized through a peer-mentoring mechanism. Instead of asking engineering students to mentor their next-in-line students on engineering dimensions, they were asked to do so on transversal skills. Students were asked to integrate a section in their reflexive note regarding mentoring. For instance, "To conclude my reflective note, I will explain the advice I would give to my mentee through my own CHIC experience", follows a list of advice related to teamwork and social skills. In a similar vein, "during the first meeting of our mentee, I quickly realized that the main problem they faced was totally different from ours, so was the group dynamic, but its

resolution may come from our experience.” A couple of engineering students nonetheless struggled with finding use in the mentoring exercise because of the timing (i.e., early in the programme).

Table 2. Assessment scheme of the final reflexive note

	Default Grade = 4		
	+1/2 point	0	-1/2 point
The length of the essay is adequate.		yes	too short/long (±50%)
Personal reflections on team work:	at least one example for what worked well/not well each.	some parts of their own team experience mentioned	own team experience not mentioned
One aspect related to interdisciplinarity OR team/individual values/goals was outlined in a concrete example	yes, and a specific "lesson learned" for a similar situation was stated	yes	no
One aspect related to team-internal communication OR meeting structure/organization was outlined in a concrete example	yes, and a specific "lesson learned" for a similar situation was stated	yes	-
The student described that (s)he interacted with their group of mentees.	-	yes / no because the mentees did not wish to be mentored	no, without reason given
Student used his/her own experience to guide the mentee	yes, and it was useful for them	yes, but it did not apply to the group/no, because it would not have applied to the group (with justification)	no, the student did not try to draw any parallels
The student's mentoring approach helped their mentee to "do differently by asking reflective questions"	yes	no, because only a directive approach worked OR aspect not visible in the essay	the mentoring approach was too directive and mentor simply told the mentee what to do
Student discovered a feature/team mechanism in the group of mentees which worked particularly well and came to a generalizing conclusion OR Student could draw personal benefit from mentoring relationship for the future (was able to generalize a situation)	yes	no/unknown	-

Whereas all engineering students comply with the assignment, one can identify differences in terms of the depth and breadth of insights in terms of disciplinary grounding, advancement through integration, and critical awareness [4]. Such differences can be attributed to the different learning experience that students went through during the programme. Interestingly enough, the level of functionality achieved by the device is not so much correlated with the quality of the reflexive dimension. One student who worked on a project achieving very limited functionalities produced a note with deep insights. The same can be said from a student who worked on a project that has the potential to be deployed in the field.

2.3 Peer-reviewing as an additional reflexive tool

Another reflexive tool has been introduced recently. Team presentations at the time of milestones are peer-reviewed. The mechanism has been introduced for two reasons: 1) keep students engaged during their peers' presentations and 2) give and gain feedback from additional persons than the faculty members. Each team is attributed another team and reviews are individual which means that each team receives 6 individual feedback sheets. Feedback touches upon form and substance with wording like "what I liked, what could be improved". Students are also asked to synthesize the most important comments and inputs from the discussion between team and faculty members following the presentation. The feedback sheets are collected, compiled and made available to teams after the milestone.

2.4 Discussion

At EPFL reflexivity towards transversal skills is not the most common assessment tool. Neither students, faculty members or administrators are accustomed to it [5]. This in turn raises a number of questions:

- Means to train reflexivity among engineering students. Setting reflexivity as an explicit learning outcome implies that students are given the opportunity to learn about and/or practice reflexivity. Whereas engineering students are often required to reflect on the engineering dimension of their projects, it much less the case on the transversal skills acquired and practiced in their projects; this is even more true in the case of an interdisciplinary project in which students are to collaborate across disciplines;
- Means to ensure the legitimacy of such an assessment mechanism among faculty members and, more broadly, academic affairs. This question can be particularly acute in an academic environment with a tradition of formal assessment methods
- Necessity to balance more "traditional" assessment methods with reflexivity;
- Timing of reflexive assessments throughout the curricula. This raises both the question of timing and frequency (e.g., less can be more);
- Means to motivate students to take a reflexive posture beyond the formal assessment requirement;
- Type of feedback to provide to the students regarding their reflexive note;
- Adequacy of reflexive notes as the mean to capture the learning attached to cross-boundary collaboration.

3 REFLEXIVITY AS AN ASSESSMENT TOOL

3.1 Lessons learnt

Akin to Heikkinen and Isomöttönen [6] we find that students generally have a positive view of multidisciplinary, that multidisciplinary teams enable students to better identify their own expertise and that very different team dynamics emerge from the tensions emerging from interdisciplinary project-based learning. This can at times lead to comments such as "it is easier to work only among engineers". As mentioned, students from different disciplines working in a team don't make an interdisciplinary team. In fact students placed in an interdisciplinary setting are usually well-aware of the different values, norms and ways of looking at problem-solving around the table. Not orchestrating the encounter runs the risk of re-enforcing some stereotypes and "inherited" disciplinary approaches. In the case of the CHIC programme, a lot of the learning activity takes places outside the classroom (e.g., when students have team meetings). Structured reflexive notes are one among several assessment methods. Combining it with peer-teaching allows students to reflect both on their own learning and on the application of their learning to a different situation.

3.2 Levers for improvement

One of the interesting recommendations by Carr et al. lies in the joint supervision of the students enrolled in an interdisciplinary doctoral programme [7]. At this stage, participants of the CHIC programme are only supervised by faculty members from their discipline. Engineering students are nonetheless encouraged to attend the “critiques” that design students undergo during the semester. All students are encouraged to attend the meetings that their team members have with their supervisors. One could imagine to include a section in the reflexive note covering these interdisciplinary “encounters”. Hoegl and Parboteeah find that among professional product development teams, team reflexivity is positively related to team effectiveness but not efficiency [8]. Social skills and project management skills are positively related to team reflexivity. One could therefore from the outset raise the students’ awareness as to the upside and downside of interdisciplinarity work using the answers to the RIPLS questionnaire as a basis. One could also introduce team reflexivity instead of individual reflexivity.

So far, transversal skills are not assessed by the engineering faculty members. One could imagine integrating a reflexive note in the final engineering report asking students to reflect on how their design choices regarding engineering have been influenced (or not) by working in an interdisciplinary team. Assessment of this part of the report could be conducted by faculty members representing the 3 institutions involved in the programme [9]. This raises the most vexing question, namely the level of involvement of faculty members in such interdisciplinary programmes, both welcomed but also seen as a distraction from their research imperatives.

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